

Advertisements Awareness About Corona Virus Pandemic Introduced To Children on MBC3 TV Channel

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
January 21,2025

Accepted:
April 23 ,2025

Keywords :

Advertisement Awareness,
MBC3, Tv Channel,
Presentation Forms

Abstract

TV Channels plays a very significant role in communicating messages nowadays. It is used as a vital means in the world of advertisements, especially in the time of Coronavirus pandemic. Thus, the current research studies the awareness of advertisements about Covid-19 introduced to kids on MBC3 TV Channel. The objective of the study is to determine the number of educational advertisements about Covid-19 presented to kids on the MBC3 channel and to disclose the methods and elements of influence used in these advertisements. A descriptive approach and survey method are utilized to study this topic. Conclusions are remarked at the end of the study like the short time, cartoon characters, focus, human voice, pictures and graphics, and lyrics as significant variables in the advertisement awareness.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15270546

Introduction

Television is one of the significant contemporary public means of mass communication, as it surpasses all other means with its ability to get the attention, astonishment and intensity of impact. It combines the advantages of radio broadcasting in terms of sound and the advantages of cinema in terms of pictures and the advantages of theater in terms of action that gives life to the scenes shown by television.

Television is also one of the important advertising mediums because of its role in delivering the advertising message to the people via motivating them to buy services or goods.

Advertising is one of the main media tools used by various establishments in order to communicate with the target audience and customers; therefore, the advertisement is of great importance in the work environment.

Advertisements have an incomparable ability to affect the child, and they are the most prominent television material and the strongest influence on the child among other materials (Tarsha, 2009, 111).

Television is considered one of the media that addresses the public and targets specific classes of the society, especially children. This increased after the emergence of many diverse and specialized television channels that have increased children's exposure to advertising content, as these channels allocate a large space for advertisements to promote products and use more influential suggestions and most capable of inducing response.

Methodological Framework

Research Problem

In light of the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic around the world, we are witnessing an alarming pattern among the various groups of society, especially the fear of families for their children and their forced to keep them at home for fear of contracting the virus in addition to the quarantine imposed on their communities and the intensification of the global recession and the suspension of schools attendance, increasing family stress levels, which led to the children not communicating face to face with friends and companions, corresponding to an increase in the hours that children spend on television screens, so are these channels able to educate children about the danger of the virus and teach them how to deal with it? Do the issue of the virus take enough space in their programs and hours of broadcast, especially specialized or directed channels for children, including the MBC3 channel, which is the subject of study.

The problem of this research is the lack of information about the educational advertisements provided by MBC3, and it can be clarified by the following question: What are the educational advertisements provided by MBC3 for children about Coronavirus?

1- Significance of the Study

The significance of this research stems from the importance of the category under study as children are an important category of society, which should be studied to know its surroundings and the influential factors in

order to properly deal with these influences and the possibility of controlling them to keep children away from negative things, especially after the emergence of the Coronavirus pandemic and the lack of relevant studies about the way children deal with this pandemic. There are no past studies dealt with this topic and all the studies that deal with this topic are considered current and up to date.

Research Objectives

- 1- Determine the number of educational advertisements about Coronavirus introduced to children on the MBC3 channel.
- 2- Know the range of information presented in these advertisements.
- 3- Disclose the methods, attraction and elements of influence used in these advertisements.

Research Methodology

The research is a descriptive one, which studies the facts about phenomena, events and existing situations by collecting data and information, analyzing and interpreting them to extract their implications or issue generalizations about them (Omar, 2002, 179).

The research is based on the survey method, where the content of the media was surveyed. The survey method works to collect information and data for a large number of people for the purpose of diagnosing or revealing their reality or part of that reality, provided that these data are collected in a limited geographical area. This type of studies may be evaluative or by assuming a scientific comparison with another study or between two elements in a particular phenomenon (Al-Qayyim, 2012, 102)

2- Research Community

The research community is the educational advertisements introduced by the MBC3 channel about Coronavirus. A comprehensive inventory of all advertisements presented through the channel has been made from the outbreak of the pandemic to the time of this research.

3- Fields of Research

Spatial Domain: MBC3

Temporal Domain: from 20/3/2020, which is the time for the first awareness advertisement on a channel, to 31/8/2020, which is the research date.

TV Advertisement and Children

The Advertisement: Conceptual and Idiomatic definition

Advertisement has become an industry based on technical and scientific foundations in which all the sciences of impact are included, starting with the principles of sensation, perception, alertness, sound, color, compound and rhythmic effects. In the advertisement, advanced degrees of television technology are practiced in order for the advertising message to come in an intense, strong, effective way that penetrates the consciousness directly and accumulates in the mind with no need for contemplation or analysis. What does matter is the emotional interaction with this message and the surrender to it and its effects (Al-Mashhadani, 2013, 4)

The advertisement is defined as the planned activity on scientific and practical bases aimed at creating a demand for a good, service, or an idea and satisfying it for certain payment, through appropriate publishing means, provided that all the technical and formal controls affected by it and influencing it are taken into account in order to have a positive effect on the audience addressed (Al-Alaq and Rababa, 2010, 136).

Advertisement is also defined as the various aspects of activity that lead to the publication or broadcasting of visual or audio media messages to the public with the purpose of urging them to purchase goods or services or in order to drive to the kind acceptance of advertised goods, services, people, ideas or facilities (Al-Bakri, 2004, 62).

Television advertisements constitute a large area in television display materials, which enhances the chances of their impact on all groups of society. However, their impact on children in particular is the most obvious, and most research indicate the increasing space of television advertisements for children. Currently, children constitute a large audience of viewers for these advertisements are due to the time they spend watching, and because certain aspects of their psychological, social and cultural formation depend on these advertisement in some way.

In this regard, Jacques Mousseau emphasized in 1976 the significance of television advertisements for the child, as these advertisements constitute, in his opinion, the child even since his early childhood. The child is like a white sheet of paper or in the words of Hoffman, he is like a piece of sponge that absorbs everything. The child acquires most of the cultural components from the environment that the media in general is one of these components. Thus, the child has a great ability to learn for many years (Ghazal, 2001, 229). Therefore, advertisement affects society in general and young people and children in particular in every way. This affect is partly due to the dazzling that usually accompanies the advertising material in addition to the repeated

broadcasting of the advertisement, which may make some foreign behaviorsto society look familiar and acceptable (Al-Karim, 2005, 176).

One of the most important goals of advertisement is the awareness and guidance that is unique to the service advertisements, which is based on directing and educating the individual in certain areas to ensure his safety from dangers or diseases. The service television advertisements that always strive to achieve this vital and important goal for viewers in developing countries have varied (Ali, 2008, 233).

Television is one of the most important cultural, informational and mass media means directed to all members of society. It is also one of the most important contemporary means of communication that connects individuals with the outside world through sound, movement and image, which contributes to presenting lively, realistic and tangible scenes and experiences. Various materials broadcasted on TV are information intended to be communicated to individuals for the purpose of using it in the fields of culture and entertainment and increasing the knowledge of the individual (Al-Wardi, 2013, 148).

Satellite channels have become a feature of contemporary reality and have occupied an advanced position among the media, as satellite channels provide the elements of immediate availability of important events for people around the world (Abdul Razzaq and Al-Samuk, 2011, 118) .

Advertising at the health level bears many considerations and is characterized by a lot of dangers at the levels of practice. In the midst of the development of the health sector and its entry into new fields, the relationship between it and advertising media has changed (Shams, 2009, 132).

Television advertisement enjoys many merits as a result of its reliance on the live picture as well as the sound, the multiplicity and diversity of the sizes of the clips used, and the possibility of controlling the enlargement of the image to be photographed, minimizing or moving it in the normal size, which helps to clarify the advertising idea and arouse the audience's interest, and then increase the effectiveness and impact of this advertisement (Al-Aalem2008, 166). Therefore, the study of television advertisement is one of the very important topics, especially that directed to the most influenced and important segments of the society, namely children.

Field Study

1- Time:

Table No. (1) shows the times of advertisement presented on MBC3

No	Ad Name	Time / Seconds	Time / Minute
1	Our health is our most valuable treasure	5	2
2	Sing With Us	18	1
3	Wash Your Hand	31	
4	Do you know where Germs live and hide?	45	1
5	Taking care of yourself is also caring for others	30	
6	Wash your Hands Now	30	
7	Learn how to sneeze and cough with your friend Karkur	30	
8	With you at home	30	
9	Stay clean and safe at home	20	1
10	Wash your hands with soap and water after the bath	41	
11	Wash your hands before lunch so that you do not eat germs	15	1
12	Wow Team: We beat Corona song	13	1
13	Wow Team: Stay at home	13	1
14	Activities for Mo friends at home		2
	Total	321 seconds	10 minutes

The number of ads on the mbc3 channel of the Corona pandemic reached fourteen ads. The duration and time of the advertisement differed according to their topics and treatments, and their total time was 10 minutes and 321 seconds.

2-Characters appearing in the advertisement:

Table No. (2) shows the characters appearing in the ads

Characters	Repetition	Percentage	Rank
Dolls	7	26.9	first
Cartoon characters	5	19.2	Scond
Cartoon characters in human form	4	15.4	Third

Dolls in the form of animals	4	15.4	Third
Male child	2	7.7	Fourth
Female child	2	7.7	Fourth
A Doll in the human form	1	3.8	Fifth
emotion	1	3.8	Fifth
Total	26	100	

The number of characters used in Corona advertisements on mbc3 channel reached 26 characters who varied between cartoon characters, dolls, human elements and emotions. The dolls ranked first with 7 characters that were repeated in the advertisements, while the cartoon characters came in the second rank, while the dolls in the form of a human and emoji came in the last place with single appearance. Through the table, we can see that cartoon characters are chosen because young children are more likely to watch programs that include cartoons and inanimate objects such as dolls that move and speak, as well as animals and other television scenes that are characterized by rapid movement and loud noises (Afra, 2005, 247).

3-Information that has been focused on in the Advertisements

Table No. (3) clarifies the information that appeared in the advertisements

Information	Frequency	%	Rank
Hand washing	11	31.4	First
Social Distancing	4	11.4	Second
Staying home	4	11.4	Second
Healthy Food	3	8.6	Third
Sterilization	2	5.7	Fourth
Use of napkins	2	5.7	Fourth
infection methods	2	5.7	Fourth
Cleanliness	2	5.7	Fourth
Sports	1	2.9	Fifth
Wearing masks	1	2.9	Fifth
Information on germs	1	2.9	Fifth
The correct way to cough and sneeze	1	2.9	Fifth
Symptoms of injury	1	2.9	Fifth
Total	35	100	

Corona advertisements on the mbc3 channel directed to children focused in its content on urging children to wash their hands continuously for a period of twenty seconds, as it was repeated 11 times, while the focus on social distancing and staying at home came second with a frequency of 4 times each, and encouraging children to eat healthy food came third with a frequency of 3 times, while sport, symptoms of injury, wearing masks, the correct way of coughing and sneezing, and information about germs ranked last, i.e. the fifth, with one recurrence.

4- The audio elements used in advertisements

Table No. (4) shows the audio elements used in advertisements

Acoustic Elements used	Frequency	%	Rank
Human voice	11	68.8	First
Music	2	12.5	Second
Silent	2	12.5	Second
Sound Effects	1	6.3	Third
Total	16	100	

Corona advertisements on the mbc3 channel directed to children used various sound elements, the most prominent of which was the use of the human voice eleven times, while music and silence occupied the second place, and the sound effects came in the last place. Obtaining the human voice in first place, this indicates the child's comprehension and understanding of directed speech and an attractive factor to him better than writing or using sound effects or music that may not arouse the attention or get realized.

5 -The Means of Explanation used in the Advertisements

Table No. (5) illustrates the means of explanation used in advertisements

Means of explanation	Frequency	%	Rank
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Pictures and graphics	9	56.3	First
numbers	2	12.5	Second
Text display	2	12.5	Second
Videos	1	6.3	Third
Games	1	6.3	Third
Signals	1	6.3	Third
Total	16	100	

Corona advertisements on the mbc3 channel directed to children used various means of explanation, the most prominent of which was the use of pictures and graphics nine times, while numbers and text display ranked second, and videos, signs and games came last. This indicates the closeness of images and drawings to the child's mind and awareness because they contain the shapes and colors that usually attract children to look at and memorize.

6- Advertisement Presentation Formats

Table No. (6) shows the ad presentation Forms

Forms	Frequency	%	Rank
Individual performance form	4	28.6	First
Lyric	4	28.6	First
Dramatic (Acting)	3	21.4	Second
Question and answer	2	14.3	Third
Dialogue form	1	7.1	Fourth
Total	14	100	

As for the methods and formulas adopted by the advertisements for Corona on the mbc3 channel directed to children to perform the advertisement, the individual form and the lyrical form were the highest frequency, and both of them ranked first with four frequencies. The dramatic form came in the second place, while the dialogue form ranked the last with one frequency. Also, the use of the singular form using a character, doll, or a child to talk about the virus, or using lyrics that talks about the virus and the ways to prevent it, are all simple forms in order to be received by children in a quick memorization and comprehension away from rhetoric and complexed speech. The individual form gives a feeling to the recipient that the speech is directed to him personally, which makes him more interested in the information presented to him.

Conclusions

1-Most of the advertisements about Corona pandemic were distinguished by a short time, which makes the viewer or child not bored with the health information addressed to him through the advertisements, even if it was repeated more than once in the channel.

2-The choice of cartoon characters and dolls was more than other characters, because young children are more likely to watch programs that include cartoons and inanimate objects such as dolls due to their proximity to children and because they are considered elements of attraction and interest to children.

3-The advertisements focused on short, specific and focused points of ways to prevent the virus, the most prominent of which was urging children to wash their hands with soap and water, which was repeated in all advertisements as it is the most important and easiest way to prevent the virus, while the rest of the prevention elements were mentioned in one advertisement and not mentioned in another advertisement.

4-The advertisements focused on using the human voice in presenting their content compared to other sounds such as sound effects and music, due to the proximity of the human voice to the child and the ease of perception of the speech directed to him and its proximity to hearing because he is accustomed to receiving advice, guidance and instructions from parents and the school.

5-The extensive use of pictures and graphics in advertisements directed at children indicates that advertisers seek to simplify information about the virus and bring it closer to the minds and eyes of children and their perception of information in a smooth manner, because it is known that children are attracted to drawings and colors in a great way, and it is one of their means of expression.

6-Advertisements directed to children focused on lyrics and individual (direct) speech to reduce scare and fear of the virus among children and display information, advice and instructions in a way close to the heart and mind of the child in a joyful, funny and simple way without intimidation, exaggeration, or glorification of the event that may confuse and frighten the child and thus distort his mind and his perception of the information.

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